

A

Appendix

5

Conclusion

In this thesis, I have shown using virtual reality that flying insects with limited computational capabilities make use of several features such as foreground segmentation, perspective, motion parallax, and integration of multiple modalities to rapidly discriminate, localize, and navigate to objects amidst a complex 3D landscape while in flight. From an algorithmic and robotics perspective, current state-of-the-art algorithms still cannot accomplish this task due to the complexity of the environment, camera motion, and computational demands¹². My results provide a template for future

application of these features that are inherent to flying insects. First, I determined that multiple species including Tephritid fruit flies (*R. pomonella*), mosquitoes (*A. aegypti*), crane flies (*P. laeta*), and hoverflies (*E. tenax*) could distinguish objects from complex visual scenery over 600 m². Each species approached objects and exhibited close-range behaviours such as object avoidance/landing responses including, in the case of hoverflies, hovering behaviour over the virtual object itself. These behaviours indicate that multiple species can visually localize and navigate to 3D virtual objects in a large complex scene (Fig. 2). I note that flying insects might potentially approach any isolated stationary object simply for the sake of landing and conserving energy, and the behavioural response to virtual objects has been shown in other studies^{15,28,29,30,31}. However, my experiments using the apple fly (*R. pomonella*) show that tethered flying insects in VR perform figure-ground discrimination, tease apart the objects in the foreground amidst a complex background from a moving frame of reference, and navigate toward a preferred target while accounting for orientation, object size and distance, self-motion, slip, airflow, and odour cues.

5.1 THE LIMITS OF VR

I note that my experiment here tested a maximum of two objects and a single directed airflow and odour flux. In natural contexts, search behaviour generally involves missing or occluded cues, clutter, and ambiguous and confounding stimuli^{116,32,35,33,36,10}. my experiments here nevertheless demonstrate prerequisites for search behaviour including figure-ground discrimination, discrimination of objects in the foreground amidst a complex background, and navigation to targets while accounting for orientation, self-motion, slip, wind, and odour cues. Future studies can include multiple or confounding targets and stimuli, deconstruct the 3D aspects of targets and their surrounding environment required for object localization, or examine the spatial and temporal structures needed for plume following and assess the impact of missing and occluded stimuli on the search

process. The insights gained in the current and future studies utilizing multimodal VR can help better understand the physiological mechanisms underlying foraging, navigation, dispersal, and mate choice in Dipterans and potentially other taxa as well. Using the rich body of knowledge we have learnt, we can harness the full potential of VR by devising ways to comprehensively present these multimodal, naturalistic stimuli matched to the insect's physiology in VR while mimicking the 3D movement in closed-loop.

5.2 VIRTUAL SURREALITY

However, VR also allows us to break the laws of nature virtually which would provide insight into how the brain works. The following few paragraphs highlight a possible few approaches that can push our understanding that is almost certainly implausible to perform in the real world.

DECOUPLING CONTRAST, GRAVITY AND OPTIC FLOW IN ORIENTATION SENSING

Knowing orientation of self is paramount for navigation, particularly flight. The orientation with respect to the celestial world decides how the forces generated by the wings affect the flight trajectory. The sky is a major cue for self orientation. The horizon and luminance difference between the sky and ground provide visual contrast, since sky is mostly brighter than the ground. The halteres/antennae and other internal organs in insects provide mechanical/gravity cues of self orientation (Idiothetic cues). Both these cues could individually or simultaneously provide orientation cues and decoupling them is challenging in the real world. To test the different hypotheses concerning how insects integrate these cues from different modalities, one can flip the sky and ground and/or flip the fly in VR. By testing insects' ability to perform on a standardized assay such as optomotor stabilization in all the combinations of the perturbations, one can tease apart the integration mechanism of mechanical and visual cues for orientation sensing.

In certain situations, the sky is not brighter than the ground. However, many insects still navigate in those conditions, such as, under canopy, clutter, light pollution and/or snow. I hypothesize that this could be due to differences in optic flow of sky and ground. Due to the inherent nature of geometry, sky and distant horizon landmarks provide only rotational optic flow, and very little or zero translational cues. On the other hand, the ground provides a mix of translational and rotation cues. By demuxing the ground signal using the sky signal one can extract orientation, translation and the degree of motion. This hypothesizes that insects have an internal model of how the sky and ground interact visually and use it for navigation.

To test internal model of optic flow structure hypothesis, one can make the sky have an optic flow as though it was the ground, while the ground to have an optic flow as though it was the sky. This can be achieved by making the terrain model with a sky texture while the sky having the ground texture. By making this world upside down, the 3D rendering will result in the flip of optic flow structure while not changing the scene luminance, as the sky is above and bright while the ground is below and dark. Similar to the previous problem, they can be tested for optomotor stabilization in all the combinations of the perturbations. The internal model would predict that when the sky and ground is flipped in optic flow structure, they would fare worse in the task than when it isn't flipped.

DECOUPLING LOOMING AND SCROLLING CUES IN MOTION PARALLAX ESTIMATION

As described earlier, deciphering depth from monocular cues is a challenge. Motion parallax can be estimated using at least two distinct visual mechanisms. One way of estimating depth is by using looming cues. By measuring the differences in the rate of change of object size, one can estimate depth. This demands a temporally coherent foreground-background segmentation followed by a measurement of the second derivative of object size. To test this hypothesis, one can artificially make a faraway tree loom as though it is a closeby tree, by expanding/contracting it instantaneously

based on the virtual position of the insect. This is as though the tree was actually a balloon which is dynamically being inflated/deflated to match the angular size of a nearby tree, while making sure the scrolling cues (see below) are unaffected. If the fly is unable to distinguish the closer tree, it suggests that they do not require looming cues in motion parallax for depth estimation.

Another way is by measuring relative differences of scrolling motion of objects. Objects which are closer swipe past the fly faster than the objects that are farther. By measuring the relative differences of side scrolling of varied objects, one can estimate relative distance of the object. To test this hypothesis, one can artificially make a faraway tree scroll as though it is a closeby tree by moving it forward/back instantaneously based on the virtual position of the insect. This is as though the tree was actually on wheels which is dynamically being push/pulled to match the scroll of a nearby tree, while making sure the looming cues (see above) are unaffected. If the fly is unable to distinguish the closer tree, it suggests they do not require scrolling cues in motion parallax for depth estimation.

In the event that they are unable to distinguish depth using either of the methods, it suggests these cues are integrated non-linearly to estimate depth and the sum is greater than the parts. On the other hand, if they can distinguish using both cues, it suggests distinct, parallel mechanisms for robust depth estimation.

5.3 CONCLUSION

VR is an excellent tool to study insect neuroethology. With the advent of faster displays, 3D printing, larger computational power, optogenetics, wide-field imaging, CRISPR, and other innovations, we can now manipulate sensorimotor, neural, and genetic mechanisms to elucidate both behaviour and its neural basis¹²³. To reduce anthropomorphic bias in our VRs, we need to sample the 3D world using high-resolution LIDARs, polarimeters, and hyperspectral imaging¹¹⁸. We must also sample the invisible yet omnipresent microcosmos of airflow and odour in the turbulent natural

world around us using light-sheet PIV, anemometer arrays, and other technologies in diverse environments¹²⁰.

If our ultimate goal in neuroethology is to push the boundaries of our understanding of animal brains, technology although necessary, it isn't sufficient. We need to be cognizant about the intricate, complex and interconnected lives of these organisms in their natural habitat. Most of these questions were answered by pioneering work from the orchards.^{6,27,132} However, the same cannot be said about many other model systems which limits our ability to infer the ecological relevance of the behaviour under study. To even have a chance at decoding the results of billion years of natural selection, we have to comparatively study diverse model organisms. To achieve these high goals, we have to get our feet wet by going to natural habitats of our model systems, understand its ecology, life history, observe their interactions with other members of the ecosystem and perform experiments in the field and the lab to understand the behaviour itself. This would not only require fieldwork and expertise of naturalists, but also require support in the form of funding and publishing. This would imply incentivising research that is often deemed as “stamp collection” or “lacking a neural mechanism” in editorial, peer review and funding decisions.

In the intersection of natural history, technology and funding, we might be able to uncover fascinating tales about the secret lives of our distant cousins. And as history has shown time and again, these unheard tales will trigger chain reactions in not only different research topics such as agriculture, epidemiology and robotics, but also on climate change and the future of humanity itself.

0.0 LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

1. P. K. **Kaushik**, M. Renz, and S. B. Olsson, “Characterizing long-range search behavior in diptera using complex 3D virtual environments,” *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.*, May 2020
2. P. K. **Kaushik** and S. B. Olsson, “Using virtual worlds to understand insect navigation for bio-inspired systems,” *Current opinion in insect science*, 2020
3. V. Parma, K. Ohla, M. G. Veldhuizen, M. Y. Niv, C. E. Kelly, A. J. Bakke, P. K. **Kaushik**, K. W. Cooper, C. Bouysset, N. Pirastu, M. Dibattista, *et al.*, “More than smell—covid-19 is associated with severe impairment of smell, taste, and chemesthesis,” *Chemical senses*, vol. 45, no. 7, pp. 609–622, 2020
4. R. C. Gerkin, K. Ohla, M. G. Veldhuizen, P. V. Joseph, C. E. Kelly, A. J. Bakke, K. E. Steele, M. C. Farruggia, P. K. **Kaushik**, R. Pellegrino, M. Y. Pepino, *et al.*, “Recent smell loss is the best predictor of covid-19 among individuals with recent respiratory symptoms,” *Chemical senses*, vol. 46, 2021
5. S. B. Olsson and P. K. **Kaushik**, “Insect decision-making,” *American Scientist*, vol. 109, no. 6, pp. 368–375, 2021

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Table A.1: Glossary of keywords

Keywords	Brief description
Closed loop	Traditional stimulus response experiments are challenging for flying insects due to their size and speed. Tethering allows one to precisely control input and measure the animal's output. But tethering leads to lack of sensory feedback of the animal's motor commands. For example, when a fly intends to turn right, it increases its left wing amplitude more than the right wing creating a rightward yaw torque. In the tethered condition, the fly's motor command will not have any effect on its visual system of being turned right (also known as open loop). By monitoring the fly's wing movements in real time and correspondingly moving the visual scenery, the fly's "intentions" are reflected back on its visual input, known as closed loop.
Virtual Reality	Continuous closed loop feedback of animal's output into its input using artificial visual cues such as image patterns on a drum, projectors, LED panels and monitor displays is what is called VR. This VR concept has extended from being vision-only to include sound, touch, taste etc.
Gain	In closed loop studies, one unit of motion of the insect corresponds to some units of motion in the virtual world, derived from electrical systems as "gain". At increased gain values, even small motions of the insect creates a large change in the virtual world and vice versa.
Optic flow	Relative motion between an animal and its environment cause visual scenes to move across different regions of its vision field at different velocities. These subtle differences in velocities give organisms, insights of their self-generated movement as well as absolute and relative size and position of objects in the 3D space from a sequence of 2D images on the retina.
Motion parallax	Insects use differences in visual cues and optic flow of landmarks, horizon, angular size and other visual characteristics over time to compute expansion rates of objects in the scenery. This provides the animal with relevant cues of relative position and absolute size of objects critical of navigation and survival.
Slip	When organisms fly in windy environments, the direction of "intended" flight or heading doesn't match the actual motion of the organism. This slight mismatch in heading and in translation direction is due to the wind dragging the organism. There is a lateral asymmetry in the optic flow, which is a function of scenery, wind speed and heading with respect to wind. Insects are known to use these slip cues to orient in the wind while flying.
Odor plumes	Odor plumes are dispersed into the air and broken into tiny packets by turbulent air. These intermittent packets drift along with the meandering wind.
Optomotor anemotaxis	Optomotor anemotaxis is upwind flight by insects guided by the wind direction and visual feedback. Insects compute their direction of motion using optic flow, motion parallax, slip and mechanical cues. These are mostly upwind flights triggered on exposure to odor plumes.

Table A.3: Bill of materials

S/L no	Item	Description	Quantity	Rate (USD)	Cost (USD)
1	2020 aluminum frame	Generic extrusions	12 m	5.6	67
2	T-Profile nuts, corner brackets	Generic extrusion attachments	30	0.7	21
3	XY plane DSLR macro slider	Neewer pro 4-way macro focus rail 10033981	1	28	28
4	Ball socket DSLR tripod head	Generic swivel head	1	4	4
5	Web camera with IR hack	Sony PS3 eye, hacked for IR pass and allow C-mount	1	4	4
6	Varifocal C-mount Lens	Pashay CP550 5-50mm C mount lens	1	21	21
7	Closed loop stepper motor	uStepper NEMA 17	1	70	70
8	Arduino microcontroller	Arduino Uno	1	4	4
9	MOSFET relay	Generic IRF540 module	1	1	1
10	High speed 3/2 solenoid valve	Landefeld M3M5 ES 24 V	1	140	140
11	Custom odor bottle	PEEK custom CNC milled	2	28	56
12	Tubing connectors and accessories	Generic T,Y and elbow push fit connectors	20	0.7	14
13	3D printed parts	Wind delivery system, lens holders, manipulators	20 h	2	40
14	IR emitter	SFH 4550, Osram	2	1	2
Sub Total					473
Optional Computer accessories based on reported system					
S/L no	Item	Description	Quantity	Rate (USD)	Cost (USD)
15	Gaming monitors	ASUS ROG Swift PG279q	3	1050	3149
16	CPU	Intel Core i7-5820K Haswell-E 6-Core	1	448	448
17	Motherboard	Asus X99 Sabertooth	1	448	448
18	GPU	Asus Geforce GTX 980 Ti	1	910	910
19	RAM	G.SKILL 32GB (8GB X 4) DDR4	1	224	224
20	SSD	Samsung 850 Pro 512GB	2	448	896
Total					6495